

I BELONG TO THIS WORLD! A TEACHER PRACTICE FOR DEVELOPING RELATEDNESS IN THE SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract:

The need for relatedness is seen as the need for human connection. Relatedness refers to the social nature of human beings and the connectedness with others. It can be stated that the person meets the needs of being related with sensitivity, warmth, emotional sensitivity and social acceptance. People need to interact with other people socially. In the self-determination theory, this need is considered necessary for people to feel mentally healthier. The aim of this study is to support development of basic relatedness skills in students, who think that they have difficulties in building relationships. The second aim of the study is to determine students' thoughts about relatedness and sense of belonging after the developed practices. In this study, qualitative research method, one of the scientific research methods, was used. It is an action research based on practice and mutual cooperation. The study group of the research consisted of 21 students from Department of Primary Education at a state university in Turkey. In this study, criterion sampling method was used. The criterion used in the study is that students emphasize that they have communication problems. The research data were obtained from (1) the semi-structured interview questions developed by the researcher, (2) the evaluation questions to answer at the end of each practice, and (3) the diaries written by students at the end of each practice. In order to collect the data of this study, a total of 7 weeks of practice was performed, six of which were the relatedness practices and one was the preparatory practice. Practices were made at the same time every week. Results showed that the students have positive thoughts about relatedness and sense of belonging after practices. According to the students, when "getting to know yourself, caring and respect, getting to know others, having a sense of belonging and developing social skills" come together, relatedness improves positively.

Keywords: need for relatedness, belonging, sense of belonging, teacher practices

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1. Introduction

Individuals acquire the human characteristics with society. A society is a group of individuals involved in persistent social interaction. After family life, the child gets into society. Society continues to educate the child. A good social environment increases the likelihood that a child will develop positive social relations. Children learn from their social environment. The social environment influences the nature and quality of the social relation. Developing and maintaining positive social relations is fundamental to a good quality of life and psychological health. Individuals who have good relationships develop a sense of belonging.

The self-determination theory mentions three basic psychological needs that are necessary for the psychological health of people. These needs are; autonomy, competence and relatedness. When these needs are satisfied, people have a psychological well-being. In other words, in environments where needs are satisfied there are people who know themselves, who value themselves, who can make their decisions freely, who are aware of their desires and what they can do, have effective relationships with their environment, and feel the belonging to the society they live in (Deci and Ryan, 1985).

This is more critical for primary school teachers. Because primary school teachers have the responsibility to train primary school students. Considering that these students are in a period open to development and learning by imitating those around them, the importance of the teacher becomes much more prominent.

People need to interact with other people socially. According to the self-determination theory, this need is necessary for people to feel healthier mentally. People need to feel that they are in contact with society, a group, their environment, or their family. Belongingness and relatedness are strong needs that are basic and growth promoting. The need to communicate and feel belonging is innate. Innate psychological needs for competence, relatedness, and autonomy concern the deep structure of the human psyche, for they refer to innate and tendencies toward achieving effectiveness, connectedness, and coherence (Deci ve Ryan, 2000).

People have a need to interact with other human beings and a need to be cared about by them. This sense of relatedness is demonstrated through social connections and a high concern for others through caring. Relatedness is the need for human connection. It refers to the social nature of human beings and the connectedness with others. It can be stated that the person meets the needs of being related with sensitivity, warmth, emotional sensitivity and social acceptance.

Based on evidence obtained in the context of self-determination theory, that the need for relatedness coexists with the need for autonomy. It can be stated that the need for relatedness should be considered together with the need for autonomy and competence (Andersen, Chen ve Carter, 2000). To feel securely attached to others, individuals have to feel a sense of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in their relationships with those others. Indeed, even when controlled for relatedness, analyses showed that the experience of autonomy with relational partners is a robust predictor of

security of one's attachment to those partners. However, although acknowledging the independent functional value of each basic need, their dynamic interactions are not ignored (Ryan ve Deci, 2000b).

Relatedness concerns the emotional and personal bonds between individuals. It reflects our strivings for contact, support, and community with others. However, relatedness implies more than just connection. Relatedness refers to the experience of connecting with others in ways that conduce toward well-being in all individuals involved (Ryan and Powelson, 1991).

Relatedness is the need to feel significant and connected to important others. Relatedness is experienced when one cares for and is cared for by important others, and is thwarted when one experiences isolation or disconnection (DeHaan, Hirai and Ryan, 2016). One of the important dimensions of relatedness is to feel belonging. Belonging is defined as students' sense of being accepted, valued, included and encouraged by others and of feeling oneself to be an important part of the life. Sense of belonging is most important in seeing value in life and in coping with intensely painful emotions. It also involves support and respect for personal autonomy.

Self-determination theory posits that satisfaction of the need for relatedness facilitates the process of internalization. In the classroom, relatedness is deeply associated with a student feeling that the teacher genuinely likes, respects, and values him or her. Students who report such relatedness are more likely to exhibit identified and integrated regulation for the arduous tasks involved in learning, whereas those who feel disconnected or rejected by teachers are more likely to move away from internalization and thus respond only to external contingencies and controls (Niemic & Ryan, 2009).

The self-determination theory emphasizes that the need for relatedness occurs in interpersonal environments throughout life. The theory assumes that intrinsic motivation is more likely to develop in environments characterized by a sense of trust and relationship. Anderson, Manoogian, and Reznick (1976) found that when children worked on an interesting task in the presence of an adult stranger who ignored them and failed to respond to their initiations, a very low level of intrinsic motivation resulted. Ryan and Grolnick (1986) and Ryan, Stiller, and Lynch, (1994) they found that children who found their teachers to be cold and uncaring were less intrinsically motivated because the teachers did not fulfill their needs of relatedness. And they showed greater intrinsic motivation in students who experienced their teachers as warm and caring. Therefore, it is thought that the problems related to the need for relatedness will affect the motivation, sense of achievement and psychological well-being of individuals (Ryan and Deci, 2000a).

Relatedness is significant for reasons beyond the promotion of psychological well-being and general school functioning. Interpersonal relationships provide the social context that supports the psychological process of internalization (Ryan and Powelson, 1991). According to researches on relatedness, children who report a greater sense of relatedness or belonging also feel more confident, cope more adaptively, show perform better in school (Ryan and Powelson, 1991; Connell and Wellborn, 1991; Lynch and

Cicchetti, 1992; Goodenow, 1993; Ryan, Stiller and Lynch, 1994; Anderman, 1999; Skinner and Snyder, 1999; Anderman and Anderman, 1999; Reis, Sheldon, Gable, Roscoe, Ryan, 2000; Ryan and Deci, 2000; Furrer and Skinner, 2003; Klassen, Perry and Frenzel, 2012).

1.1 Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study is to support development of basic relatedness skills in students, who think that they have social relationship problems or difficulties in building relationships. The second aim of the study is to determine students' thoughts about relatedness and sense of belonging after the developed practices. Within the scope of this aim, answers to the following questions were sought:

- 1) What do the students think about the characteristics of healthy relationships or need for relatedness after the practices?
- 2) How do the students evaluate the change in their social relationships after practices?
- 3) How do the students evaluate themselves about sense of belonging after the practices?

2. Method

This section contains information about the research model, participants, data collection process, data collection tools and data analysis method.

2.1. The Research Model

In this study based on practice and mutual cooperation, action research one of the qualitative research method was used. The focus of this study is to develop an activity-based practice for teachers. Practices and research were combined for aim of this research.

At the end of the action research carried out in this study, an original model for teacher practices is proposed. The proposed model consists of lesson plans. Expert opinions were taken at every stage of the activity-based practices and the content of practices was shaped in line with these views. In addition, problems or troubles that occurred during the practices were tried to be corrected in the next practice. Students' needs for relatedness were determined while the process was going on. Therefore, each practice is a pilot practice for the next practice.

Face to face interviews and document analysis techniques were used to obtain the data of this research. Content analysis was conducted on the data obtained from face-to-face interviews and diaries written by the students.

2.3. Participants

The study group of the research consisted of 21 students from Department of Primary Education at a state university in Turkey. In this study, criterion sampling method was used to select the participants. The criterion used in the study is that students emphasize that they have communication problems.

Before starting the practices, interviews were conducted with 97 students and they were asked two questions.

- 1) Do you have problems about the sense of belonging?
- 2) Do you have trouble building relationships with people?

Among the 97 students who answered these questions, 21 students who thought that they had problems with social relations were included in the study group.

Five of the students participating in the study are male and the others are female. The average age of the students is 20 years. The academic achievement score of 21 students at Faculty of Education is between 1,98 and 3,52 in the scoring system which is the maximum is 4. Their mean scores are 2,45. Six of the participants live with their families, 15 of them live in state dormitories or private dormitories. Participants generally stated that their income levels were "low" or "middle".

2.4. Data Collection Tools

The research data were obtained from (1) the semi-structured interview developed by the researcher to use in interviews with students, (2) the evaluation questions to answer at the end of each practice, and (3) the diaries written by students at the end of each practice. After all the practices were completed, the students were asked the following questions.

- 1) What did you think about the requirements of a healthy relationships and relatedness after the practices?
- 2) How do you evaluate yourself about relatedness after the practices?
- 3) What kind of changes happened in your social relations after the practices?
- 4) What did the practices make you think about the sense of belonging? Did you feel yourself belong to a place or a group?

2.5. Data collection process and action plan

Practices were made at the same time every week. The practices were carried out in the drama classroom of the Faculty of Education. The classroom is a very convenient place to play. In the classroom there are seating cushions, a chair for everyone, sound system and projection. In order to collect the data of this study, a total of 7 weeks of practice was performed. Six of them were the relatedness practices and one was the preparatory practice. The data collection process is given in detail in the figure 1, below.

Figure 1: Action research process

A. First Practice: Meeting with the study group

Creative drama method was used for the first practice. During the practice, which is carried out using ball, pen, crayons, paint brush, drawing paper and yarn ball, was used also moving music for some activities. Loudspeakers and music players are required for activities with music playing in the background. During the preparation section of the practice, "Name Chain, Cold-Fire and the Meaning of my Name" games were played. Dialogues on daily relationships with the role playing and improvisation techniques were exhibited. At the end of the activity, mind maps about social relations were drawn by students and students were asked to write their diary. A total of 8 activities were used in the practice. The objectives of the practice are determined as follows:

- Knows the names of those in the group.
- Realizes the individual characteristics of group friends.
- Realizes the interpersonal differences.
- Collaborates with the group.
- Realizes the requirements of effective communication.

B. First Practice for Relatedness: Creative drama

For the first practice about relatedness, one of the psychological needs, the expert opinion was consulted. After the feedbacks, necessary arrangements were made and first practice about relatedness applied to the group.

Creative drama method was used for the first practice for relatedness. Moving music was also used in the practice, which was carried out using balls, paper, pens, crayons, newspaper news and mind maps. Using the role playing and improvisation techniques, dialogues explaining the importance of social relations in life were exhibited. During the practice, "hot seating" and "freeze frames" techniques were also used. The practice consists of a total of 6 activities. At the end of the practice, personal diaries were distributed in for the participants to write their evaluations. The objectives of the practice are determined as follows:

- Realizes the importance of social relationships in life.
- Realizes the value of being a member of a group, a society.

C. Second Practice for Relatedness: Literary works and musical show

The activity of literary works, which is the second practice related to relatedness, was presented to the expert opinion and applied to the group after it was prepared with the necessary arrangements.

In the practice, Oğuz Atay's novel titled "Tutunamayanlar", Engin Geçtan's work titled "İnsan Olmak" and Peyami Safa's novel title "Yalnızız" were used. The dialogues selected from the books were read out loud and the main ideas in the dialogues were discussed. During the practice, quotations on "relationships, loneliness, sense of belonging, effective communication" were also used. During the evaluation stage of practice, 6 different poems were written by the participants with station technique and then these poems were converted into musical format. Below are some dialogs used during the practice.

A passage for the book titled "Tutunamayanlar":

"If you will forget me one day, if you leave me one day, don't tire me out. Don't take me out of my cave."

"There was a lot to be told. So, I was silent. If I said one, the other would be half. Did you hear the things I kept silent about?"

A passage for the book titled "İnsan olmak":

"Human relationships are similar to the story of a group of hedgehogs that encounter on a cold day. The hedgehogs snuggle together to get warm, but their spines sink. When they leave each other, they are disturbed by the cold. By moving back and forth, they finally find the best distance to warm each other without sinking their thorns."

A passage for the book titled "Yalnızız":

"In the middle of large crowds, the social creature, called human, is a prisoner of his own inner world and is doomed to healing loneliness."

"Because silence is the worst answer."

This practice was formed according to the following objectives:

- Recognizes the value of feeling as a member of a group or a society.
- Knows communication channels outside of speech to understand people and tell himself.

D. Third Practice for Relatedness: Photos, caricatures and pictures

The practice plan using photos, pictures and caricatures about relatedness was rearranged by taking into consideration the group needs determined during the previous practice. The practice plan was applied to the group after being prepared by taking the expert opinion.

During the practice, photographs and caricatures on "cities, people, communication, friendship, social groups" were used. During the evaluation section, the participants were asked to draw their own pictures about the relatedness.

This practice was created for the following objectives:

- Realizes the importance of social relationships in life.
- Realizes the value of being a member of a group, a society.
- Makes self-assessment.

Some pictures drawn by students are given below.

Picture 1: Pictures drawn by students for Photos, Caricatures and Pictures Practice

E. Fourth Practice for Relatedness: Games

Lesson plan consisting of communication games related to relatedness has been implemented. For this practice, games called “Parasite Game, Name Ball, Write Five Important Numbers, Give Your Most Valuable Object, Make Your Friend's Commercial, Make Eye Contact with People Standing in Circle” were used. This practice was created according to the following objectives:

- Makes an effort to get to know people.
- Understands the importance of eye contact.

F. Fifth Practice for Relatedness: Paired practices

For this practice, “Choose your friend, talk to him and share your project” activity has been implemented. The names of those in the group were written on the bingo bag and everyone was asked to choose a person's name. Partners are formed in this way. Different role cards were distributed to each partner. The couples spoke themselves about “social relations, loneliness and sense of belonging” for 30 minutes and prepared a 5-minute presentation to explain the matter to the other participants. This practice was created according to the following objectives:

- Thinks about psychological and behavioral effects of being excluded.
- Realizes the requirements of a healthy social relationship.

G. Sixth Practice for Relatedness: Scenarios and video shooting

This practice was carried out by using videos taken by students outside the classroom. A few days before this practice, students were divided into 6 groups. Each group was asked to prepare scenarios and shoot short videos, which they also played. The content of the scenarios was about effective social relationships, relatedness and a sense of belonging. During the practice, videos taken outside the faculty were watched and discussed. This practice was created according to the following objectives:

- Realizes the requirements of a healthy social relationship.
- Feels the value of feeling as a member of a group or a society.

2.6. Validity and reliability of the study

Merriam (1998) proposed various strategies such as getting opinions from a colleague about the findings, getting the data checked to the data source, expressing own views and thoughts of the researcher at the beginning of the study, and involving the participants in the whole process in order to ensure internal validity in the case studies. For the internal validity of the study, raw data were checked with the students and member checking was provided. The research report is presented in detail to ensure the credibility of the study and to make the reader believe that the findings are safe.

All the activities used in the research were written by the researcher and the objective statements (acquisition) of the practice plans were created by examining the literature. The created practice plans were examined by a lecturer specialized in Turkish Education, a lecturer from the Department of Painting and a lecturer who had academic studies on self-determination theory. In line with the opinions received, the practice plans were created. Problems or troubles that occurred during the practices were tried to be corrected in the next practice. Students' needs for relatedness were determined while the process was going on. Therefore, each practice is a pilot practice for the next practice.

2.7. Data analysis

Content analysis technique was used to analyze the data of the research. Direct quotations are included to reflect the thoughts of the individuals interviewed. The interview data were examined by a field specialist, and codes and themes were created. The data obtained through the interview were first transferred to the text in accordance with the qualitative research techniques, and then content analysis was conducted. The main purpose in content analysis is to reach concepts and relationships that can explain the collected data.

3. Findings

3.1. Findings about the defining of need for relatedness

The students were asked what the practices suggest about relatedness and the requirements of a healthy relationship and what can be done to make social relations more effective. Answers to this question are collected in nine categories.

The students made many different definitions regarding the concepts of social relation or effective sociality and they associated the relatedness with many variables (Figure 2). According to them (1) self-assessment, (2) trying to get to know people (3) being enterprising and courageous, (4) sharing, (5) being compatible, (6) eliminating prejudices, (7) thinking positive, positive attitudes and behaviors, (8) making friends, (9) having common values and goals with people, (10) being tolerant are necessary and important for healthy relationships.

Figure 2: Categories related to relatedness

The students in the study group were asked about how they behaved in the past related to social relations. The students were asked to evaluate the positive situations they experienced in relation to healthy relationships by comparing them with their previous experiences. The students explained that in the past, they did not care about the effective ways of communication they realized through practices, moreover they did the opposite of what they learned today in the past.

Table 1: Findings about the past and the present of the students related to social relations

	What I did before the practices	What I think after the practices	Frequency (f)
1	Self-alienation, not discovering yourself	Self-assessment, self-confidence	16
2	Not caring for people	Getting to know people	12
3	Shyness, shame	being enterprising and courageous	9
4	Incompatibility	being compatible	7
5	Avoiding sharing	Sharing something	7
6	Constant judgments	Eliminating prejudices	7
7	Negative attitude, negative thinking	Acting positive and thinking positive	6
8	Escaping from people	Making friends	5
9	Only personal values are important	Having common goals or values	4
10	Intolerance	Tolerance	4

As it can be seen from Table 1, while the students explain what they did before the practices, they mentioned the actions such as “being a stranger to yourself, not caring about people, shyness, shame, incompatibility, keeping yourself from sharing, having unchanging judgments about people, negative attitude, negative thinking, being in the shell, escaping from people, being intolerant and worthlessness of others' values”.

It can be said that after the relatedness practices, the students realized that their past behaviors caused social problems. It was determined that 16 students had the opportunity to make “self-assessment” about their social relations through relatedness practices. These students believe that social relations cannot be carried out without getting to know themselves well. According to them, alienation is a preventive factor for self-evaluation.

As can be seen from Table 1, 12 students realized that it is important to know people for relatedness. According to them, communication can be more effective if efforts are made to get to know people.

9 students stated that their social relationships are always negatively affected because they act selectively. In fact, they are afraid of people. The student named S12 expressed his thoughts as follows:

“I thought through practices that I am a social person. Actually, I am a social person, but I withdraw myself. Sometimes I feel afraid of people. In the past, I didn't want to be with people, and I thought people thought negative to me. I need to change this, I don't know if I can, but I will try.” (S12)

7 students felt that it was important to be compatible during the practices. The students started to think that their desires could not always be fulfilled and in some cases, it might be necessary to refer to the opinions of others.

Some students have realized that sharing a feeling, a thought, a common goal, a material, a possibility is necessary for relatedness. Getting rid of prejudices is one of the issues that students emphasize. They stated that they started to believe that approaching people without prejudice could lead to many positive changes. They also stated that they learned that they could establish healthy social relations by getting rid of their prejudices. It has been determined that some students have gained awareness about “acting positive” or “positive thinking” in social relations. According to them, having a negative attitude towards people is one of the biggest obstacles to healthy social relationship.

There are 4 students who explain that efforts should be made to make friends. Warm, friendly and close friendships are essential for relatedness.

Having common goals or common values is important for relatedness. Students think that the sense of partnership causes them to feel closer to someone. 4 students believe that tolerance is a key concept. Below are some quotes from students' words.

"In this practice we made the mask of our three-favorite people, but it took a lot of time. The part of holding on to our own face and making it speech was challenging. I have never thought of "me" in the eyes of my mother, father and brother." (S1)

"I realized that the essential thing in living is social relations. Communication, family... I realized that we need everyone around us." (S2)

"Body language... ..I noticed things that I have not seen in myself before. I spoke to my body." (S5)

"Making friends feed my hunger. How many people I had the same idea with them! I'm happy." (S9)

"Although we think differently, we were able to work when we had a common goal. This means that productive work can be done without thinking the same thing with people." (S10)

"I like to know what people think about me. I was able to observe people. This was a very different feeling. Every person is called a different world. Here I really felt it." (S14)

"Can one be happy when he is alone? I can't be. I'm happy with the people around me." (S20)

3.2 Findings related to sense of belonging

After the practices, the students were asked what they thought about the sense of belonging to the society. As can be seen in Table 2, students' responses on sense of belonging constituted 5 main categories. The answers given to the question were categorized as "being loved", "feeling valuable", "feeling of happiness", "loving people" and "believing that it is necessary". Only one student attributed negative sense to the sense of belonging. According to him, belonging is a bad thing and ties the hand of man.

Table 2: Categories related to feeling of belonging after practice (When do we belong?)

Sense of belonging	Categories	I understood that...	Frequency (f)
Positive perspective	Being loved	I feel belonging because I am loved by people.	7
	Feeling valuable	I feel belonging because I see value.	5
	Feeling of happiness	I feel belong when I am happy.	4
	Love people	I feel belonging because I love society.	2
	The thought of necessity	I feel belonging because it should belong to society.	2
Negative perspective	Shackles	Feeling belonging is captivity.	1

7 students explained that when they were satisfied with the pleasure of being loved by someone, they felt that they belonged to a place or a group, namely the society. It is understood that they felt belonging to the society because they were loved or when they were loved. The students named S4, S8 and S21, stated the following regarding the subject.

"Belonging... When I feel like belonging to a place, it is when I am happy and not bored. Every place that is boring me and foreign to my ideas seems to me far and cold." (S4)

"I really saw myself as part of the university. How nice it feels to belong to a city or to belong to an institution." (S8)

"I realized that I need people to love me. I had a good time. We laughed, had fun. A friend of mine said to me, "How nice you are." Then I felt close to him." (S21)

5 students from the participants stated that they have a sense of belonging because they feel valuable in the society they live in. In other words, the participants feel belonging when they see value. The student named S11 said the following about the subject:

"Everyone respected me. "I'm precious," I said. They cared about my ideas. I made a lot of friendships when I saw value. I realized that this is what was missing so far." (S11)

4 of the students stated that they had fun and were happy during the practices. They explained that they felt belonging to the group because they were happy. The student named S10 explained that he enjoyed spending time with people, in other words, he felt a sense of belonging because he loved the society.

2 students mentioned that they can feel belonging when they love people. 2 students, on the other hand, explained that they believed that it was necessary to feel belonging to a group, a place, a community.

"A sense of belonging is a human need, just like the need for food or water." (S5)

For the student named S2, the sense of belonging to the society means being captive. According to him, belonging is like a shackles. That shackles disturb S2 so much that he wants to get rid of his sense of belonging. In other words, "sense of belonging" has a negative meaning for him. The thoughts of S2 on the subject are as follows:

"Yes. In our practices I noticed that actually, I don't do things for myself. I always do things for people, for the family. We are very obsessed with what people say. Being one of the community, mediocrity. I think being captive to belong to the community." (S2)

Students were asked where they felt themselves belong. As seen in Figure 3, the answers of the students participating in the study constituted seven different categories. These categories are where they live, their families, schools, countries, professions, friends and everything that is beautiful.

Figure 3: Findings about sense of belonging. Where do you belong to?

4. Conclusion and Discussion

In this study, which was carried out in order to develop the competencies related to the relatedness of students who think that they have problems in the context of social relations and to investigate the students' sense of belonging, it was seen that the students developed positive thoughts about relatedness and belonging. Thanks to the relatedness practices the students realized their behaviors that they thought caused social problems.

Figure 4: Final results about relatedness

In Figure 4, there are categories that are thought to be related to relatedness. According to the participants of this study when "getting to know yourself, caring and respect, getting to know others, having a sense of belonging and developing social skills" come together, relatedness improves positively. Niemiec and Ryan (2009), also mention a similar situation about caring and respect. Strategies for enhancing relatedness include conveying warmth, caring and respect to students. After the practices, students noticed the mistakes they made with the relatedness.

It was seen that some of the students had the opportunity to make "self-assessment" about their social relations through relatedness practices. Others have gained awareness of "acting positively" in social relations. In the study conducted by Arslan, Erbay and Saygın (2010), it was also concluded that creative drama positively affected the communication skills of students.

After the practices, some students stated that they learned to be positive in their behavior towards people. The works of Tanrıseven and Aykaç (2013) support this result. In the study, it was concluded that drama activities contributed to the students to decrease shyness, to express themselves more easily, to communicate, to adapt to the group and to empathize.

It was seen that some of the students have a sense of belonging because they feel valuable in the society they live in. Some students stated that sense of belonging is important for happiness and therefore they feel belong to society. According to Anthias (2006) people belong together when they share values, relations and practices and it is a central dimension of life.

When the process is evaluated in general, it is concluded that the students' ability to cooperate with the group has improved. Similarly, Namdar and Çamadan (2016) reached the conclusion that creative drama practices with teachers have a positive and meaningful effect on their social skills. In the study conducted by Kara and Çam (2007), it was found that the effect of creative drama method was positive on gaining social skills such as working with the group, starting and maintaining the relationship and self-control. Based on research, in elementary school, children's reports of the quality of their relationships deal with their positive coping, self-esteem, school engagement, relative autonomy, and engagement in school (Ryan, Stiller and Lynch, 1994; Wentzel, 1994)

5. Suggestions

- 1) Opportunities can be created for students to get to know themselves first and then others.
- 2) Opportunities can be created in the school environment for students to have a sense of belonging.
- 3) Students can be encouraged to make friend and to learn positive friendship skills and group activities can be activated.
- 4) Activity based studies can be carried out to develop social skills.

- 5) In universities, conferences can be organized to emphasize the importance of basic psychological needs for the individual to discover himself and establish healthy relationships with himself and his environment.
- 6) In the drama lessons given at Faculty of Education, a separate time can be devoted to psychological needs. In this way, practices about autonomy, competence and relatedness in drama lessons can be organized with prospective teachers.
- 7) This study was carried out with the students of Primary Education Department. Similar research can be done with elementary school students or teachers from different branches.

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